

Beyond Open Research: Developing a Proof-of-Concept to Embed Quality and Reliability

Workshop 2: Using the SCOPE framework to recognise quality, reliability and Team Science

Developing a collaborative approach to recognising and incentivising quality and reliability

OPTIONS

PROBE

	RECOGNITION	KNOWLEDGE SHARING	TRAINING	DIVERSITY
Require all members to have an ORCID		Create a skills database with regular updates and monitoring	Mandatory training (e.g., diversity, mental health), CPD every 6 years	Track diversity in roles, backgrounds, and outputs
Acknowledge mentoring, teaching, supervision , considering personal circumstances		Track time spent sharing skills (e.g., via PDR)	Use of PRES (Postgraduate Research Experience Survey) and departmental surveys	Use HR systems and databases
Award schemes for excellence in extra activities		Conduct anonymous staff surveys on collaboration	Collect demographic data to assess diversity and inclusion	Leverage external databases
Include extra activities in performance reviews		Record training sessions/workshops attended or led	Combine quantitative (attendance) and qualitative (feedback) data	Promote public engagement
Use a merit/credit taxonomy		Offer recognition prizes	Implement evaluation mechanisms	Use ORCID and Symplectic to track contributions
Employ AI for credit attribution		Include skill-sharing in promotion criteria or job descriptions	Introduce scaffolded training from early stages	
Promote licensing awareness and a culture of giving credit			Encourage peer mentoring and peer observation	
Ensure transparent division of responsibilities			Use external auditors	
			Conduct Annual Review Conversations (ARC)	
Risk of preferential treatment and unconscious bias		Tech-phobia, overstated contributions, database reliability	Survey fatigue and pressure on already busy staff	Gaming metrics by inflating role diversity
Need for transparency and rigorous processes		Overburdening of junior staff, carers, part-time workers	Non-representative feedback	Privacy issues in HR data
Potential over-reliance on AI		Low survey response rates and inaccuracy	Career risks tied to demographic disclosures	Security risks with external data
Challenges in clearly attributing responsibilities		Time cost of training and sharing	Time-intensive data collection	Incomplete capture of outputs
Ensuring equity in recognition across roles and circumstances		Risk of bias in recognition or exclusion of certain staff groups	Ineffective evaluations if not well-designed	Overemphasis on diversity at the expense of research quality
			One-size-fits-all training may not suit all roles	Role model fatigue among underrepresented groups
			Bias in student feedback	